

Unraveling the diversity of secondary metabolites from Sordariomycetes by metabolomics

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List of Publications

- I **Charria-Girón E**, Surup F, Marin-Felix Y (2022). Diversity of biologically active secondary metabolites in the ascomycete order Sordariales. *Mycological Progress* 21:43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11557-022-01775-3>.
- II Cedeño-Sanchez M¹, **Charria-Girón E**¹, Lambert C, Luangsa-ard JJ, Decock C, Franke R, Brönstrup M, Stadler M (2023). Segregation of the genus *Parahypoxylon* (Hypoxylaceae, Xylariales) from *Hypoxylon* by a polyphasic taxonomic approach. *MycKeys* 95:131-162. <https://doi.org/10.3897/mycokeys.95.98125>.
- III Wongkanoun S, Chainuwong B, Kobmoo N, Roytrakul S, Somrithipol S, Luangsa-ard J, **Charria-Girón E**, Srikitikulchai P, Stadler M (2023). Studies on the genus *Pyrenopolyporus* (Hypoxylaceae) in Thailand using a polyphasic taxonomic approach. *Journal of Fungi* 9(4):429. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof9040429>.
- IV **Charria-Girón E**, Stchigel AM, Čmoková A, Kolařík M, Surup F, Marin-Felix Y (2023). *Amesia hispanica* sp. nov., producer of the antifungal class of antibiotics dactylfungins. *Journal of Fungi* 9(4):463. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof9040463>.
- V **Charria-Girón E**, Marin-Felix Y, Beutling U, Franke R, Brönstrup M, Vasco-Palacios AM, Caicedo NH, Surup F (2023). Metabolomics insights into the polyketide-lactones produced by *Diaporthe caliensis* sp. nov., an endophyte of the medicinal plant *Otoba gracilipes*. *Microbiology Spectrum* 11(6):e0274323. <https://doi.org/10.1128/spectrum.02743-23>.
- VI Toshe R, **Charria-Girón E**, Khonsanit A, Luangsa-ard JJ, Khalid SJ, Schrey H, Ebada SS, Stadler M (2024). Bioprospection of tenellins produced by the entomopathogenic fungus *Beauveria neobassiana*. *Journal of Fungi* 10(1):69. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jof10010069>.
- VII Pfütze S¹, **Charria-Girón E**¹, Schulzke E, Toshe R, Khonsanit A, Franke R, Surup F, Brönstrup M, Stadler M (2024). Depicting the chemical diversity of bioactive meroterpenoids produced by the largest organism on Earth. *Angewandte Chemie* 63(16):e202318505. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202318505>.
- VIII **Charria-Girón E**, Sauer C, García D, Ebada SS, Marin-Felix Y (2024). Neochetracin: An unusual chetracin-type epithiodiketopiperazine derivative produced by the fungus *Amesia atrobrunnea*. *ACS Omega* 9(22):24009–24014. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.4c02424>.

- IX** Kobmoo N, Mongkolsamrit S, Khonsanit A, Cedeño-Sanchez M, Arnarnart N, Noisripoom W, Kwantong P, Sonthirod C, Pootakham W, Amnuaykanjanasin A, **Charria-Girón E**, Stadler M, Luangsa-ard JJ (2024). Integrative taxonomy of *Metarhizium anisopliae* species complex, based on phylogenomics combined with metabolomics, morphometric analyses, and virulence data. *IMA fungus* 15(1): 30. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43008-024-00154-9>.
- X** **Charria-Girón E**¹, Zeng H¹, Gorelik T, Truong KN, Pahl A, Schrey H, Surup F, Marin-Felix Y (2024). Arcopilins, a new family of *Staphylococcus aureus* biofilm disruptors from the soil fungus *Arcopilus navicularis*. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 67(17):15029–15040. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.4c00585>.
- XI** Harms K¹, **Charria-Girón E**¹, Stchigel AM, Marin-Felix Y, Surup F (2024). Reaping the chemical diversity of *Morinagamyces vermicularis* using feature-based molecular networking. *Journal of Natural Products* 87(9):2335-2342. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jnatprod.4c00654>.
- XII** Hoyos LV, Vasquez-Muñoz LE, Osorio Y, Valencia-Revelo D, Devia-Cometa D, Große M, **Charria-Girón E**^{*}, Caicedo-Ortega NH^{*} (2024). Tailored culture strategies to promote antimicrobial secondary metabolite production in *Diaporthe caliensis*: a metabolomic approach. *Microbial Cell Factories* 23(1):328. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12934-024-02567-y>.

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Weitere Publikationen

- XIII** Niego AGT, Lambert C, Mortimer P, Thongklang N, Rapior S, Große M, Schrey H, **Charria-Girón E**, Walker A, Hyde KD, Stadler M (2023). The contribution of fungi to the global economy. *Fungal Diversity* 121:95–137. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13225-023-00520-9>.
- XIV** **Charria-Girón E**, Vasco-Palacios AM, Moncada B, Marin-Felix Y (2023). Colombian fungal diversity: Untapped potential for diverse applications. *Microbiology Research* 14(4):2000-2021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microbiolres14040135>.
- XV** Zdouc MM, Blin K, Louwen NLL, ..., **Charria-Girón E** et al (2024). MIBiG 4.0: advancing biosynthetic gene cluster curation through global collaboration. *Nucleic Acids Research* gkae1115. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkae1115>.

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Tagungsbeiträge

Charria-Girón E (November, 2021). Colombia, the lost treasure in the search of new natural products. Challenges and opportunities for new bioactive molecules from Colombian biodiversity, BMBF meeting, Medellín, Colombia.

Charria-Girón E (March, 2022). Explorando la diversidad colombiana como fuente de nuevos compuestos antimicrobianos: Una mirada desde la metabolómica. Invited talk Universidad Francisco de Paula Santander, Cúcuta, Colombia

Charria-Girón E (December, 2022). Colombia, an untapped source of benefiting fungi. Invited talk Universidad de Antioquia, Medellín, Colombia

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Charria-Girón E (May, 2023). Unraveling the secondary metabolite diversity in the Sordariomycetes by metabolomics. HZI PhD assembly, Saarbrücken, Germany

Charria-Girón E (September, 2023). Metabolomics insights into the production of cytochalasans by xylariaceous fungi. Cytolabs retreat (DFG FOR-5170), Burg Warberg

Charria-Girón E (March, 2024). Use of OMICs for drug discovery. Seminar of the Centre of Excellence in Fungal Research, Mae Fah Luang University, Chiang Rai, Thailand

Charria-Girón E (August, 2024). Integrated omics insights into the diversity of cytochalasans: A discovery approach. Cytolabs symposium (DFG FOR-5170), Braunschweig, Germany

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Posterbeiträge

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Charria-Girón E, Vasco-Palacios AM, Caicedo NH, Beutling U, Marin-Felix Y, Surup F, Stadler M (2022). Hongos endófitos colombianos, fuente de nuevos metabolitos secundarios. First Colombian mycological congress, Bogotá, Colombia

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Declaration of Contribution to the Publications

The contributions of the author Esteban Charria-Girón (EC-G), as well as of the co-authors of the respective publications are stated below:

- I** Conceptualization: EC-G, FS and YMF; data collection and curation: EC-G, and YMF; writing—original draft preparation: all authors. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.
- II** Conceptualization: MC-S, EC-G and MS; specimen collection: MC-S and CD; methodology and investigation: MC-S, EC-G and MS; visualization: MC-S and EC-G; writing—original draft preparation: MC-S, CL and EC-G; writing—review and editing: all authors. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.
- III** Conceptualization: SW, NK, MS, JIL and EC-G; specimen collection: SW and PS; culture characterization: SW; methodology and investigation: SW, BC, NK, MS, PS and EC-G; data curation and interpretation: SW, EC-G, NK, and MS; visualization: SW, NK and EC-G; writing—original draft preparation: SW, EC-G, NK and MS; writing—review and editing: all authors. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.
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1. Symbols and Abbreviations

3D ED	3D electron diffraction
3GCRE	Third-generation cephalosporin-resistant Enterobacterales
BBH	BiOTEC Bangkok Herbarium
BCC	BiOTEC Culture Collection
BGC	Biosynthetic Gene Cluster
BPI	U.S. National Fungus Collections
BRFT	Brown rice solid medium
CBS	Centraalbureau voor Schimmelcultures, Utrecht, the Netherlands
CCF	Culture Collection of Fungi in Prague
CDCl ₃	Chloroform
CHIKV	Chikungunya Virus
COSY	Correlation spectroscopy
CPE	Cytopathic effect
CRAB	Carbapenem-resistant <i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>
CRE	Carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae
DAD	Diode array detection
DCM	Dichloromethane
DMEM	Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
DSM	German Collection of Microorganism and Cell Cultures
ECD	Electronic circular dichroism
ESI	Electrospray ionization
EtOAc	Ethyl acetate
FBMN	Feature-based molecular network
FMR	Collection of the Facultad de Medicina y Ciencias de la Salud, University Rovira i Virgili
GC-MS	Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry
GCF	Gene cluster family
GNPS	Global natural products social molecular networking
HMBC	Heteronuclear multiple-bond spectroscopy
HPLC	High performance liquid chromatography
HRESI-MS/MS	High-resolution electrospray ionization tandem mass spectrometry
HSQC	Heteronuclear single-quantum spectroscopy
IC ₅₀	Half-maximum inhibitory concentration
LC	Liquid chromatography
<i>m/z</i>	Mass to charge ratio
MAA	Microporenic acid A
MeCN	Acetonitrile
MeOH	Methanol
MF	Molecular family
MHB	Mueller–Hinton Broth
MIC	Minimum inhibitory concentration
MOI	Multiplicity of infection

MS	Mass spectrometry
MS/MS	Tandem mass spectrometry
MTPA	α -methoxy- α -(trifluoromethyl)phenylacetyl chloride
MUCL	Strain accession number of the Mycotheque de l'Université catholique de Louvain, Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium
NMR	Nuclear magnetic resonance
NRPS	Nonribosomal peptide synthetases
NYGB	New York Botanical Garden
OD	Optical density
OFT	Whole oat solid medium
PCA	Principal component analysis
PKS	Polyketide synthase
PLC	Preparative liquid chromatography
ROESY	Rotating frame nuclear Overhauser effect spectroscopy
RP	Reversed phase
SAR	Structure-activity relationship
STMA	Strain accession numbers of the Culture Collection of the Microbial Drugs Department, Helmholtz Centre for Infection Research, Braunschweig, Germany
TAR	Transformation-associated recombination
TOCSY	Total correlation spectroscopy
TOF	Time-of-flight
UHPLC	Ultrahigh-performance liquid chromatography
UHPLC-DAD-IM-MS/MS	Ultrahigh-performance liquid chromatography coupled with diode array detection and ion mobility tandem mass spectrometry
UPLC	Ultra-performance liquid chromatography
UV-Vis	Ultraviolet/visible (light)
WHO	World Health Organization
WT	Wild type
YM 6.3	Yeast-malt extract liquid medium
YMA	Yeast-malt extract solid medium

2. Summary

Fungi belonging to the class Sordariomycetes represent one of the most diverse and ecologically important groups within the Ascomycota, with many taxa playing significant economic roles through their biotechnological applications. While some of these fungi produce a unique array of secondary metabolites, compounds that play a critical role in their ecological interactions and have led to novel therapeutics, systematic studies into their chemistry remain limited, even at the genus or family level in some orders. Moreover, despite decades of natural products research, several challenges persist. The complex taxonomic history of these fungi, recently reshaped by molecular tools, has left many genera without clear documented natural products, and the classification of many producers remains uncertain. This thesis presents a pilot study exploring the diversity of secondary metabolites in Sordariomycetes, with a focus on the Hypocreales, Sordariales, and Xylariales, by combining advanced metabolomics with traditional chemical screening of well-defined taxa. This practical approach bridges modern taxonomic revisions with the chemical diversity of these fungi, reduces the re-isolation of known compounds, and prioritizes efficiently promising candidates for in-depth studies.

As an initial step, a compound library from secondary metabolites produced by members of the family Hypoxylaceae was constructed, and later expanded to include both known molecules and crude extracts from other fungi. This repository proved essential for chemotaxonomic studies by enabling high-throughput evaluation of sample novelty and the detection of common chemical scaffolds useful for taxonomic discrimination. In parallel, several strains from unexplored taxa were cultured in diverse liquid and solid media, and the obtained extracts were analyzed by using the established metabolomics approach. Following dereplication and evaluation of their biological properties, promising strains were selected for scaled-up cultivation. Their extracts were subsequently fractionated using various chromatographic techniques, and the purified compounds were structurally elucidated through a combination of modern chemical methods. Collectively, these efforts led to the discovery of 34 unprecedented secondary metabolites and the identification of 12 new taxa within the Sordariomycetes, advancing our understanding of fungal secondary metabolism and laying the groundwork for future investigations beyond the scope of this thesis.

3. Introduction

3.1. Fungi and Antibiotics: A Historical and Modern Perspective

Fungi have long been silent heroes, shaping not only the resilience of ecosystems and nature as a whole but also the development of society. Building on the growing understanding of fungal biology, recent advancements have improved our ability to harness their potential to address major global challenges, including human health (Hyde et al. 2019, Case et al. 2025). In fact, prior to the discovery of modern antibiotics, fungi were exploited for their medicinal properties. Although early civilizations lacked knowledge of the underlying mechanisms, they recognized the value of fungi, incorporating them extensively into both their diets and traditional medicine. Many civilizations continue these practices today. For example, in traditional Chinese medicine fungi play a central role, with numerous species contributing significantly to it, and representing a big economical share of this market (Niego et al. 2023). Recent estimates suggest that fungi contribute profoundly to the global economy, with their value reaching approximately USD 54.57 trillion, an indication of their immense importance to modern society, mainly through their roles in carbon trading and sequestration. This remarkable figure not only underscores their economic impact but also serves as a reminder of what might be lost if our actions do not contemplate its conservation (Meyer et al. 2020, Mapook et al. 2022, Niego et al. 2023).

The serendipitous discovery of penicillin by Alexander Fleming marked the beginning of the “Golden Era” of antibiotics. While studying bacterial cultures, Fleming observed that a fungal contaminant, later identified as *Penicillium rubens* (Houbraken et al. 2011), inhibited the growth of surrounding bacteria, leading to a groundbreaking moment. Life before modern antibiotics was drastically different, with common infections often proving fatal. One of the key factors behind the significant increase in life expectancy over the past century has been the widespread availability of antibiotics. The success of penicillin not only revolutionized modern medicine but also accelerated advancements in microbiology and natural product chemistry (Lobanovska and Pilla 2017). The 20th century witnessed an unprecedented surge in antibiotic discovery, largely driven by systematic screening efforts from pharmaceutical companies. These initiatives led to discovering major antibiotic classes, including aminoglycosides (e.g., streptomycin),

tetracyclines, and macrolides, predominantly derived from bacteria (Harvey et al. 2015, Newman and Cragg 2016).

On the fungal side, most clinically relevant natural products have been sourced from taxa within the Ascomycota, with only a few originating from the Basidiomycota (Bills and Gloer 2016). These include cephalosporins, derived from *Acremonium* spp., as well as fusidic acid and griseofulvin, which remain in clinical use. However, despite the vast number of fungal secondary metabolites described, only a handful have been developed into marketable drugs (Mapook et al. 2022). Nevertheless, those that have reached the market have proven indispensable to medicine, playing a crucial role in disease management while also representing significant economic value (Niego et al. 2023). Figure 1 illustrates the evolution of the antibiotic pipeline since the discovery of penicillin, with a particular focus on antibiotics originating from or inspired by fungal metabolites.

Figure 1. Timeline of the antibiotic pipeline with an emphasis on antibiotics originated from fungi.

Despite these advancements, the widespread use of antibiotics has also given rise to one of the greatest challenges in modern medicine, antimicrobial resistance. With great power comes great

responsibility, and society has vastly contributed to the emergence of multidrug-resistant microbes (Dickey et al. 2017). The inadequate use of antibiotics in clinical settings, self-medication, and intensive application in animal breeding, have not only accelerated the spread of antimicrobial resistance but also reduced the number of treatment options. In parallel, the decline in discovery efforts by many of the world's largest pharmaceutical companies has placed us in a critical situation (Cooper and Shlaes 2011). Most antibiotics in use today are still based on compounds first discovered in the 20th century (Rossiter et al. 2017). However, many of these drugs have undergone extensive synthetic or semisynthetic modifications to improve their pharmacological properties and, to some extent, combat resistance (Atanasov et al. 2021) (Figure 2). Yet, despite these efforts, the situation continues to deteriorate. Resistance mechanisms continue to evolve, spreading even to last-resort antibiotics and leaving clinicians with limited options against multidrug-resistant pathogens (Heimann et al. 2025). Fighting antimicrobial resistance requires a comprehensive approach that integrates infection prevention efforts, surveillance, responsible usage and access to therapeutic treatments, as well as an increase in research and development. The World Health Organization (WHO) has classified bacterial pathogens according to their risk into critical, high, and medium priority groups, in order to prioritize research efforts worldwide (WHO 2024). The critical pathogen group includes Carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* (CRAB), carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CRE), and third-generation cephalosporin-resistant Enterobacterales (3GCRE), highlighting the severe lack of effective therapeutic options, as these pathogens are now resistant to last-resort antibiotics. While investment to counteract the spread of resistance is fundamental, it is still not sufficient, primarily due to the lack of economic profitability for the pharmaceutical sector (Engel 2020). It is important to note that the current antibiotic crisis extends far beyond economic profitability, which is why several funding initiatives were established to combat the issue, sadly remaining insufficient when compared to the rapid emergence and spread of drug-resistant infections (Heimann et al 2025).

The limited success of semisynthetic derivatives from known antibiotics stems from their shared molecular targets, making them susceptible to existent resistance mechanisms (Rossiter et al. 2017, Atanasov et al. 2021, Miethke et al. 2021). This underscores the need for research focusing

on discovering novel chemical entities with distinct modes of action, such as the recently introduced pleuromutilins. These diterpenoid antibiotics, produced by certain species of *Clitopilus* (Agaricales, Basidiomycota), were first identified over 70 years ago. However, their clinical development was initially hindered by low production yields as well as poor pharmacokinetic properties during in vivo assays, requiring extensive optimization efforts (Mapook 2022). At the time of their discovery, advancements in synthetic biology and fungal biotechnology were not as developed as today. It took several decades to establish a reliable, multi-gram production platform for these compounds. Despite these challenges, the heterologous expression of the pleuromutilin biosynthetic gene cluster (BGC) in *Aspergillus oryzae* has now been achieved (Bailey et al. 2016, Alberti et al. 2023). The development of a sustainable production process for pleuromutilin and other structurally unique terpenoids through synthetic biology provides new hope for the field, as these metabolites have a different target than currently used antibiotics (Alberti et al. 2023, Tian et al. 2025). The above examples reaffirm the role of natural products in addressing resistance while stressing the untapped potential of diverse fungal groups, a promise that we hope to unlock.

Advancements in molecular tools have significantly improved our understanding of microbial diversity, particularly among fungi. Recent estimates suggest that the number of expected fungal species ranges between 2.2 and 3.8 million, with other projections reaching up to 12 million (Hawksworth and Lücking 2017, Phukhamsakda et al. 2022, Cazanonne et al. 2024). These figures are far greater than the number of species currently reported. With the growing availability of molecular tools, we can only hope that the identification of these species, which has historically been a major challenge, will become more efficient. In parallel, many previously neglected fungi are now being isolated, studied, and deposited in international culture collections, making them available for in-depth investigation, particularly with respect to secondary metabolite production (Bills and Gloer 2016, Atanasov et al. 2021). Our understanding of fungal biosynthetic capacities has advanced significantly, leading to the concept that secondary metabolites have evolved alongside their producers and their ecological adaptations, followed by tailored biological properties contributing to their survival. As a result, taxonomic diversity is closely linked to

chemical diversity, representing not only a major frontier of knowledge for researchers in fungal natural products but also a source of hope for the discovery of novel antibiotics.

Figure 2. Examples of antibiotic classes derived from fungi and their semisynthetic derivatives. **(A)** Penicillins and their four generations of semisynthetic derivatives: penicillin V (1st), nafcillin (2nd), amoxicillin (3rd), and piperacillin (4th). **(B)** The five generations of cephalosporins and their semisynthetic derivatives: cefazolin (1st), cefuroxime (2nd), ceftazidime (3rd), cefepime (4th), and ceftaroline (5th). **(C)** Pleuromutilins, the most recently introduced class of antibiotics derived from fungi, along with their semisynthetic derivatives.

3.2. Xylariales: An Untapped Source of Bioactive Natural Products

The order Xylariales represents one of the largest within the Ascomycota and includes species of significant ecological importance across diverse ecosystems. Many genera within this order

exhibit distinctive life cycles, with some species developing conspicuous or inconspicuous stromata (Figure 3), while others persist predominantly in their anamorphic state as endophytes (Stadler 2011, Wendt et al. 2018). Additionally, some members have been reported from a wide range of environments, including marine ecosystems (e.g., *Halorosellinia oceanica*, syn. *Hypoxylon oceanicum*), symbionts of invertebrates (e.g., *Daldinia eschscholtzii*), and even coprophilic species (e.g., *Stromatoneurospora*, *Podosordaria*, and *Poronia*) (Schlingmann et al. 2002, Zhang et al. 2008, Becker et al. 2020). Specialized lineages in the order have developed high degrees of host specificity. For instance, termite-associated genera (Rogers et al. 2005) or *H. fraxinophilum*, which exclusively colonizes *Fraxinus* spp. (Stadler et al. 2008), whereas other taxa, such as *D. eschscholtzii* and *Entoleuca mammatum*, can colonize a broad range of substrates (Stadler et al. 2014, Rogers & Ju 1996). Moreover, species like *D. loculata* persist in extreme environments by developing resilient stromata capable of withstanding fire-induced stress (Stadler et al. 2014).

Such ecological adaptations have contributed to the evolution of secondary metabolite pathways and the development of complex symbiotic interactions. These taxa are recognized as a megadiverse source of bioactive secondary metabolites, many of which feature unique carbon skeletons not found in other fungal groups. For example, the azaphilones found in the stromata of species within *Hypoxylon* and closely related genera exemplify how speciation can drive the tailoring of common biosynthetic pathways (Kuhnert et al. 2021). Unfortunately, the exact biological functions of these molecules remain largely obscure, and their production, which is restricted to stromata rather than cultures, constitutes a significant challenge for their systematic study. Similarly, cytochalasans are also present in the stromata of certain taxa, but they are also found in cultures of certain genera (Becker and Stadler 2021). Other prominent stromatal metabolites include hypoxyvermelhotins, found in only two taxa within the order (Kuhnert et al. 2014, Wongkanoun et al. 2025), as well as the carneic acids from *H. carneum* (Quang et al. 2006). Stromata of the genus *Hypomontagnella monticulosa* (syn. *Hypoxylon monticulosum*) apparently lack pigments. However, metabolites derived from their cultures often yield intriguing chemistry. Notably, the sporothriolides and sporochartines from *Hyp. monticulosa* denote a unique class of fungal metabolites, namely alkyl citrates (Surup et al. 2014, Tian et al. 2020). Other interesting

metabolites obtained from cultures are the topoisomerase I inhibitor hypoxyxylone from *H. fragiforme* (Piettre et al. 2002), the rare polyketide macrolides rickiols (Surup et al. 2018), and the abietane-type diterpenoid rickitin from *H. rickii* (Kuhnert et al. 2015). Similarly, the mantis-associated *D. eschscholtzii* produces highly complex polycyclic polyketides known as dalesconols, which show strong immunosuppressive activities and are biosynthesized via a radical coupling mechanism (Zhang et al. 2008). Additionally, terphenyls such as fendleryls are produced by *H. fendleri* (Intaraudom et al. 2017). Detailed reviews on the diversity of secondary metabolites among Xylariales taxa can be found in the studies by Helaly et al. (2018) and Becker and Stadler (2021).

Recent studies on selected species have revealed unique and complex metabolites. For example, an endophytic *Xylaria* sp. was found to produce the eremophilanolide sesquiterpene xylareremophil, for which an asymmetric total synthesis was achieved (Wang et al. 2025). Total synthesis of the 3-phenyl isoindolinone daldinans was also accomplished, revealing the presence of atropisomerism around the C-3–C-8 axis (Kamauchi et al. 2024). The unprecedented caged xanthone [6,6,6,6] polyketide daldipyrenones, featuring a spiro-azaphilone unit, were isolated from an endolichenic *D. pyrenaica* (Lee et al. 2023). Furthermore, the cyclic tetrapeptides pseudoxylallemycins were isolated from a termite-associated *Pseudoxylaria* sp., with some congeners possessing a rare allene moiety (Guo et al. 2016). Beyond their intriguing chemical structures, compounds from the Xylariales have significant therapeutic potential (Helaly et al. 2018, Becker and Stadler 2021). For example, some members produce antiparasitic nodulisporic acids, certain taxa are able to synthesize antimycotic sordarins, *Xylaria* spp. produce the widely used antifungal griseofulvin, and species within the Xylariaceae contribute to the production of the marketed drug emodepside (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Stromata of selected taxa from the Xylariales. (A) *Annulohypoxyton* sp.; (B) *Durotheca comedens*; (C) *D. macrostroma*; (D) *Entonaema* sp.; (E) *Hypoxyton luteogranulatum*; (F) *Pyrenopolyporus bambusicola*; (G) *H. haematostroma*; (H) *H. aeruginosum*; (I) *H. polyporoidium*; (J) *Entonaema* sp.; (K) *Daldinia flavogranulata*; (L) *Poronia pileiformis*; (M) *Podosordaria elephanti*; (N) *Xylaria allantoidea*; (O) *X. cubensis*; (P) *X. escharoidea*; (Q) *X. telfairii*; (R) *Xylaria* sp. Photos taken by Sarunyou Wongkanoun.

Historically the taxonomy of the Xylariales has been marked by considerable challenges, with concepts used to differentiate key genera undergoing drastic changes. Traditionally, the order was regarded as a homogeneous lineage based primarily on the morphological traits of asci and ascospores. However, the significant morphological and phenotypic plasticity observed has hindered the delineation of clear-cut subdivisions beyond the family level. A unique feature of many ascomycetes and basidiomycetes is their heterokaryotic stage, an intermediate phase between plasmogamy and karyogamy, which reflects the flexible sexual strategies that fungi employ. In several species, the reduction of sexual processes in the teleomorph (sexual form) and the occurrence of genetic recombination in the anamorph (asexual form) require maintaining these distinct morph terms, rather than simply referring to "asexual" and "sexual" stages (Kirschner 2019). For instance, one of the first comprehensive taxonomic studies of the Xylariaceae distinguished the genus *Xylaria*, characterized by geniculosporium-like anamorphs, from genera related to *Hypoxyton*, which exhibit nodulisporium-like anamorphs (Ju & Rogers 1996). The genus *Xylaria* is one of the most ubiquitous genera, distinguished by its erect, often branched stromata and dull-pigmented ascospores in comparison with hypoxyloid taxa (Wendt et al. 2018).

In addition to morphology, the work of Whalley and Edwards (1995) included chemotaxonomy as a counterpart to traditional morphology-based taxonomy, thereby enhancing the verification and consolidation of taxonomic concepts within the order. This integrative approach is now well accepted, particularly given that certain stromata-forming taxa contain pigment granules that reveal species-specific colors upon KOH treatment, a diagnostic tool particularly useful within the Hypoxylaceae (Stadler et al. 2011, Wendt et al. 2018). Systematic analyses of these pigments have revealed remarkable secondary metabolite diversity, with some species producing up to 20 structurally related compounds, primarily azaphilones and binaphthalenes (Becker et al. 2021).

Notably, stomatal metabolite profiles remain highly conserved within species, regardless of origin or environment, and can even persist for centuries (Kuhnert et al. 2015, Surup et al. 2018).

Figure 4. Selected secondary metabolites from taxa belonging to the Xylariales.

Phylogenetic analyses based on conserved genomic sequences across fungal species have advanced the resolution of evolutionary affinities among these taxa. For example, Hsieh et al. (2005) recognized the genus *Annulohypoxylon*, corresponding to the sect. *Annulata* as defined by Ju and Rogers (1996). Although early phylogenetic approaches provided poor resolution of hypoxylid taxa (Triebel et al. 2005), later multi locus phylogenetic analyses incorporating both protein-coding genes and rDNA have become the gold standard for studying *Hypoxylon* and its allies (Kuhnert et al. 2014, 2017, Sir et al. 2016). Currently, the Xylariales comprise 22 families and include up to 56 genera with uncertain placement (Wijayawardene 2022). The largest family within the Xylariales has traditionally been the Xylariaceae, although recent taxonomic revisions have led to its segregation into several families based on polyphasic approaches, including chemotaxonomic affinities (Wendt et al. 2018, Daranagama et al. 2018). Among these changes, the family Hypoxylaceae was resurrected to accommodate species that often form ascomata embedded in stromatal tissue on dead wood, such as those previously classified within *Hypoxylon* and allied genera. Recent taxonomic surveys within the Xylariales integrate polyphasic, or integrative, approaches that combine traditional morphological traits with multi-locus gene genealogies and chemotaxonomic evidence, resulting in comprehensive taxonomic concepts for the delimitation of genera and even species.

Despite these efforts, some of the most relevant and largest genera, such as *Xylaria* and *Hypoxylon*, remain paraphyletic. Taxonomists face several challenges with these groups, including the lack of type material for direct comparison and the limited availability of genomic sequences, which restricts the scope of phylogenetic studies. However, in an effort to establish a robust framework for genomic investigations of the model family Hypoxylaceae, high-quality genome sequences of selected, taxonomically well-characterized representatives from the major phylogenetic clades within the family have recently become available (Wibberg et al. 2021). Phylogenomic analyses based on these data have confirmed prior hypotheses derived from polyphasic taxonomic studies, as the resulting tree topologies are consistent with those obtained from multigene-based calculations, although with higher statistical support, thereby providing a strong phylogenetic backbone for subsequent studies on the evolution of these organisms (Wendt et al. 2018). Although this pilot study does not capture the full taxonomic diversity of the

Hypoxylaceae, and even less so at the order level, it established a solid framework for a broad range of investigations, including studies on fungal evolution, population dynamics, host-fungus interactions, biodegradation, and the biosynthesis of secondary metabolites. Inspired by the diversity of secondary metabolites within Hypoxylaceae and the availability of high-quality genome sequences, the biosynthetic potential of these organisms was investigated to estimate their true potential as secondary metabolite producers (Kuhnert et al. 2021). This led to the identification of 783 biosynthetic pathways across the fourteen studied species, mostly organised in BGCs, which constituted 375 gene cluster families (GCFs). Notably, only ten GCFs were found to be conserved across the studied taxa, highlighting how speciation in Hypoxylaceae influences secondary metabolism. While this just marks the first step towards uncovering the intricate potential of the members of the Xylariales, the fact that most of GCFs could not be linked to known products in the Hypoxylaceae provides an optimistic prospect for the future discovery of secondary metabolites produced by these taxa.

3.3. Neglected Taxa in Sordariales: Uncovering Their Biosynthetic Potential

Similarly to the Xylariales, fungi belonging to the Sordariales order denote a taxonomically diverse lineage, with species occupying various ecological niches, including soil, lignicolous, herbicolous, and coprophilous habitats (Huhndorf et al. 2004, Marin-Felix et al. 2020). While certain taxa are widely recognized as model organisms in genetics (*Neurospora crassa* and *Triangularia anserina*) (Davis and Perkins 2002, Hensen et al. 2023), production of secondary metabolites (*Chaetomium*, *Rhyphophila*, and *Pseudorhyphophila*) (Vicente et al. 2009, Harms et al. 2021, Ibrahim et al. 2021), and industrial enzyme production (*Thermothelomyces thermophilus*) (Hutchinson et al. 2019), most of the genera within the order remain largely overlooked. One could argue that this is partly due to challenges in their isolation, as some genera are relatively ubiquitous and found across diverse substrates, whereas others are rather rare and much more ecologically restricted (Marin-Felix and Miller 2022). Additionally, the classification of its genera has historically been challenging, and ongoing efforts continue to refine and achieve a more natural classification of its taxa. In fact, the taxonomic framework used for the Sordariales has undergone significant changes over the years, particularly with the advent of DNA-based

methods, which have revealed phylogenetic relationships that were previously obscured by morphological plasticity. In many cases, the ascospore morphology has proven insufficient to resolve phylogenetic relationships within certain genera, whereas characteristics of the ascomatal wall appear more useful for delimiting taxa. Polyphasic studies have demonstrated that *Gelasinospora* and *Neurospora* form a single monophyletic lineage within the Sordariaceae despite their distinct ascospore ornamentation (García et al. 2004). This highlights the importance of integrating multiple lines of evidence through integrative taxonomy, including molecular phylogenetics in addition to traditional morphological studies. Regrettably, the availability of molecular data is lacking for several taxa within the Sordariales and future efforts are required to corroborate their taxonomic placement. Figure 5 illustrates the diversity of the ascomata morphologies among members of the Sordariales.

As in the Xylariales, polyphasic taxonomy integrating morphological and molecular data is now widely accepted for the Sordariales (Marin-Felix and Miller 2022). However, unlike members of the Xylariales, such as *Hypoxylon*, species within the Sordariales typically do not form stromata, which limits the applicability of chemotaxonomy as a reliable taxonomic tool. Nevertheless, studies on secondary metabolites produced in culture have provided valuable taxonomic insights for certain taxa, for instance, the discovery of sordarins restricted to the Naviculisporaceae family and zopfinols in *Pseudorhizophila* species (Harms et al. 2021). In this context, the Sordariales are as well recognized as prolific sources of structurally diverse natural products, with significant untapped potential. For instance, in well-studied families such as the Chaetomiaceae, even though the number of reported secondary metabolites exceeds 400 distinct compounds, novel metabolites continue to be discovered, particularly in less studied genera (Ibrahim et al. 2021). This suggests that the taxonomic diversity within the Sordariales is closely linked to their biosynthetic potential. As new genera continue to be erected through taxonomic revisions, many remain unexplored in terms of secondary metabolism, as exemplified by species within *Amesia* (Publications IV and VII). Consequently, investigating the secondary metabolites of these overlooked taxa could significantly contribute to expanding the known chemical space (Hoffmann et al. 2018). Further details on the diversity of biologically active compounds produced by fungi in this order can be found in **Publication I** of this thesis. Recently, the first attempt to establish a

phylogenomic framework for the study of this order was conducted, providing valuable insights into genomic trends within the Chaetomiaceae, Podosporaceae, and Sordariaceae (Hensen et al. 2023). These trends may reflect diverse ecological adaptations, evolutionary events, and other key traits. However, dedicated studies on the biosynthetic diversity of this fungal group are still lacking, opening avenues for new research directions that could help unravel the evolutionary history of these intriguing organisms.

Figure 5. Morphological variability found in the Sordariales. A–E: Ascomata. (A) *Areotheca areolata*. (B) *Triangularia arizonensis*. (C) *Corynascus fumimontanus*. (D) *Jugulospora rotula*. (E) *Amesia hispanica*. F, G: Asci. (F) *Corynascus fumimontanus*. (G) *Jugulospora rotula*. H–M: Ascospores (H) *Amesia hispanica*. (I) *Rhyphophila decipiens*. (J) *Naviculispora terrestris*. (K) *Jugulospora rotula*. (L) *Neurospora indica*. (M) *Neurospora tetrasperma*. Scale bars: A = 200 μm ; B, D = 100 μm ; C, E = 50 μm ; I = 20 μm ; F, G = 15 μm ; H, J, L, M = 10 μm , K = 5 μm . Pictures A, B, D, G, I–K adapted from Marin-Felix et al. (2020); C, F from Marin-Felix et al. (2015); E, H from Charria-Girón et al. (2024); L, M from Garcia et al. (2004).

3.4. Advances in OMIC-based Technologies and Their Application to Natural Products Discovery

While conventional approaches have led us to groundbreaking discoveries over decades, particularly in the case of new antibiotic scaffolds identified through high-throughput discovery campaigns, recent advancements in analytical techniques for screening, isolation, characterization, and optimization of natural products are now revolutionizing the field or expected to do so (Atanasov et al. 2021, Mallowney et al. 2023). As discussed in previous sections, the current scenario has shifted dramatically compared to the previous century. Today, the urgency to combat antibiotic resistance is evident, however, financial constraints continue to be challenging. Ironically, although we now possess a deeper understanding of how much remains unknown, we still struggle to effectively prioritize efforts and resources toward the most promising “hits”.

In recent years, the advent of the DNA era has granted access to affordable sequencing technologies, enabling us to obtain whole-genome sequence data from diverse organisms (Choi and Kim 2017, Hyde et al. 2019, Chen et al. 2023a,b). Simultaneously, computational tools for analyzing these extensive datasets have rapidly evolved, enhancing our ability to decipher genetic information, particularly biosynthetic genes and pathways associated with the production of metabolites (Miethke et al. 2021, Blin et al. 2023). The process of identifying genes or gene clusters responsible for the biosynthesis of natural products is now widely referred to as genome mining. This approach is feasible largely because biosynthetic genes are often physically clustered within the genomes of producer organisms and regulated by the same mechanism (Blin et al. 2023). Additionally, many of these BGCs contain megasynthases, such as polyketide

synthases (PKSs) and nonribosomal peptide synthetases (NRPSs), which encode large, modular enzymes with highly conserved domains (Medema and Fischbach 2015). These conserved features allow computational algorithms to efficiently detect and classify BGCs, enabling the discovery of novel secondary metabolites (Navarro-Muñoz et al. 2020). Even though a major pitfall of these “rule-based” tools or algorithms is their limitation to detect or predict BGCs that conform to known biosynthetic classes, often failing to identify “non-canonical” biosynthetic genes, there is still significant room for improvement (Konkel et al. 2024). Nevertheless, the field has expanded considerably with the widespread adoption of genome mining campaigns as a central element of natural product discovery pipelines (Miethke et al. 2021). These approaches provide a solid foundation for future discoveries by offering a broad overview of the biosynthetic landscape harbored by microbes, although regrettably, much of this potential remains inaccessible.

In parallel, molecular biology tools dedicated to engineering biosynthetic pathways have advanced to provide access to the “dark matter” of the biosynthetic space by cloning and expressing BGCs heterologously in well-studied host organisms such as *Escherichia coli*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Aspergillus oryzae*, etc. (Tian et al. 2025). However, challenges such as the correct expression of regulatory elements, post-translational modifications, and precursor availability complicate the successful heterologous expression of BGCs. Many biosynthetic pathways rely on complex regulatory networks that are not easily recapitulated in a heterologous host, leading to incomplete or inefficient expression (Atanasov et al. 2021, Augustijn et al. 2024). Moreover, certain biosynthetic enzymes may require specific chaperones, cofactors, or subcellular localization to function properly, adding an additional layer of complexity. To overcome these challenges, synthetic biology approaches have been employed, including pathway refactoring, the use of tailored expression cassettes, and metabolic engineering strategies to optimize precursor supply and intracellular balance of cofactors. Additionally, recent advances in CRISPR-based tools and large-fragment DNA assembly methods, such as transformation-associated recombination (TAR) in yeast and Cas9-mediated in vivo assembly, have significantly improved the ability to manipulate large genomic regions, thereby facilitating the activation and study of cryptic BGCs (Kurylenko et al. 2024, Lee et al. 2024, Xie et al. 2024).

Despite these advancements, the field still faces hurdles in scaling up these approaches for industrial applications and ensuring that heterologous expression systems can faithfully reproduce the native biosynthetic conditions required for efficient production.

In line with current molecular biology paradigms, the final level of specific phenotypes is linked to the metabolic state at a given time point, which is essentially captured as a snapshot of the metabolites produced by a specific organism in that moment. Metabolomics has emerged as a powerful field, driven by technological advances in chromatography and spectrometry, enabling comprehensive analysis of the chemical space within biological samples and providing insights into the biological processes occurring under specific conditions. The integration of metabolomics approaches into natural product discovery pipelines has significantly accelerated and streamlined the analysis of the vast datasets generated from microbial screening campaigns (Wolfender et al. 2019, van der Hooft et al. 2020). These workflows enable high-throughput analysis and dereplication of biological samples, facilitating a deeper understanding of the complex chemical diversity inherent to microbes, particularly fungi (Stadler et al. 2007). For instance, metabolomics aids in the prioritization of novel chemistry by predicting and identifying unprecedented carbon skeletons while also addressing challenges such as resource waste due to the re-isolation of known compounds (Ceasar et al. 2021, Scherlach and Hertweck 2021). Metabolome mining has greatly benefited from the development of the Global Natural Products Social (GNPS) molecular networking platform (Wang et al. 2016), which facilitates the organization of large datasets and visualizes relationships between diverse molecules. This approach is based on the hypothesis that structurally similar metabolites exhibit comparable fragmentation patterns in tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) experiments. While the benefits are undeniable, several limitations and constraints affect the reach and resolution of these methods (van der Hooft et al. 2016, Vitale et al. 2024). Consequently, results generated by these algorithms should be considered exploratory and serve primarily as a guide for prioritization during screening campaigns. Once promising hits are identified, further experimental validation through classical chemical screening workflows remains essential (Ayon et al. 2024, Kostka et al. 2024), including scaled-up cultivation, preparative chromatography, NMR-based structure elucidation, and biological evaluation of the isolated metabolites.

4. Aims and Outline of the Thesis

In the previous sections, the untapped potential and the associated challenges of studying fungal secondary metabolism were discussed, particularly in the context of discovering novel anti-infectives and combating the spread of antibiotic resistance. Fungi from certain lineages within the Sordariomycetes have emerged as unique reservoirs of biologically active natural products, however, these taxa have not been systematically investigated and remain largely neglected. The advent of modern molecular tools, ranging from advanced sequencing techniques to tandem mass spectrometry tools, has reinforced the need to study these unexplored organisms. In fact, these tools have not only opened new avenues for uncovering fungal biosynthetic potential but have also provided insights into fundamental questions, such as the relationship between taxonomic and chemical diversity.

The work presented in this thesis aims to expand our understanding of the biosynthetic potential of neglected taxa within the Sordariomycetes. To achieve this, state-of-the-art metabolomics approaches were integrated into classical screening workflows, consequently enhancing the performance of dereplication efforts and facilitating targeted prioritization of novel bioactive molecules. The application of 4D-metabolomics enables the multidimensional characterization of fungal metabolomes, improving our understanding of their complex and diverse chemical space. Building on our extensive expertise in fungal taxonomy and secondary metabolism, we developed a curated fungal metabolome library that captures the chemical diversity inherent within the Sordariomycetes, with particular emphasis on the Hypoxylaceae. The extensive collection of natural products isolated during prior chemotaxonomic studies of this family served as the basis for this repository, which was subsequently expanded to encompass compounds from other fungal groups, including metabolites derived from polyketide, NRPS-like, NRPS, PKS-NRPS, terpene, and meroterpenoid pathways. The established metabolomics workflow was subsequently employed for the study and chemical characterization of neglected taxa during our ongoing screening campaigns. This integrative approach enabled the prioritization of promising taxa for scale-up cultivation and the targeted purification of bioactive components. The data generated herein provide a solid foundation for elucidating biosynthetic relationships among these fungi and pave the way for future metabologenomic mining campaigns.

5. Materials and Methods

5.1. Fungal Material

The fungal strains studied in this thesis were provided by different collaborators from geographically diverse locations worldwide. Detailed information regarding their isolation, morphological description, and multigene phylogenetic analysis can be found in their respective publications (Table 1). All taxonomic studies and phylogenetic analyses were conducted with the support of Dr. Yasmina Marin-Felix, Dr. Aida M. Vasco-Palacios, Dr. Noppol Kobmoo, MSc. Artit Khonsanit, Dr. Alberto M. Stchigel, Dr. Dania García, Dr. Marjorie Cedeño-Sanchez, Dr. Christopher Lambert, Dr. Cony Decok, Dr. Jennifer J. Luangsa-ard and Prof. Dr. Marc Stadler.

Table 1. Fungal strains investigated during the course of this study.

Order	Family	Genus	Species	Deposition number	Paper	
Agaricales	Physalacriaceae	<i>Armillaria</i>	<i>ostoyae</i>	DSM 115711	IX	
Diaporthales	Diaporthaceae	<i>Diaporthe</i>	<i>caliensis</i>	CBS 149729	VI	
Hypocreales	Cordycipitaceae	<i>Beauveria</i>	<i>neobassiana</i>	BCC 31604	VIII	
Hypocreales	Clavicipitaceae	<i>Metarhizium</i>	<i>spp.</i>	Refer to Table 1 of publication XI for further details	XI	
Sordariales	Chaetomiaceae	<i>Amesia</i>	<i>atrobrunnea</i>	FMR 19325	X	
			<i>hispanica</i>	CBS 149852	IV	
		<i>Arcopilus</i>	<i>navicularis</i>	CCF 3252	XII	
	Schizotheciaceae	<i>Morinagamyces</i>	<i>vermicularis</i>	CBS 303.81	XIII	
Xylariales	Hypoxylaceae	<i>Parahyphoxylon</i>	<i>papillatum</i>	BPI 591029	II	
				BPI 591035		
				NYGB 830462		
				NYGB 830463		
				STMA 08016		
		<i>Pyrenopolyporus</i>	<i>laminosus</i>	<i>bambusicola</i>	BBH47923	III
				<i>cinereopigmentosus</i>	BBH47927	
					BBH47928	
					MUCL 53305	
					BBH47924	
	<i>macrosporus</i>	BBH15197				
	<i>tonngachangensis</i>	BBH25392				

5.2. Metabolomics Workflow and Analytical Procedures

This workflow was designed to comprehensively characterize secondary metabolites, focusing on their accurate detection, annotation, and classification. It integrates optimized mass spectrometry methods for the optimal profiling of diverse chemical entities. Advanced data processing, including dereplication using in-house spectral libraries and *in silico* tools, facilitated the identification of known and novel metabolites. Additionally, molecular networking and high-throughput prioritization supported chemotaxonomic studies and the selection of promising fungal strains. All MS spectra were initially evaluated using Bruker DataAnalysis software (version 6.1; Bruker Daltonics) followed by metabolomics analyses conducted with MetaboScape® 2022 (Bruker Daltonics). Technical and analytical support for mass spectrometry measurements was provided by Ulrike Beutling and Aileen Gollasch, while untargeted metabolomics workflows were designed under the supervision of Dr. Raimo Franke.

5.2.1. HPLC–DAD/MS Analysis

Crude extracts and pure compounds were dissolved at concentrations of 4.5 and 1 mg/mL, respectively, in a 1:1 solution of acetone and methanol. Then, ESI-MS spectra were recorded in both positive and negative ion modes using an UltiMate 3000 Series uHPLC (Thermo Fischer Scientific, Waltman, MA, USA) equipped with a C18 column (Acquity UPLC BEH 1.7 μ m, 2.1 \times 50 mm; Waters, Milford, MO, USA) and a sample injection volume of 2 μ L. The system was coupled to an amaZon speed ESI-Iontrap-MS (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) and the mobile phase consisted of A (H₂O + 0.1% formic acid) and B (ACN + 0.1% formic acid) with a constant flow rate of 0.6 mL/min. The gradient started at 5% B for 0.5 min, increased to 100% B in 20 min and was held at 100% B for 10 min. The column temperature was maintained at 40°C, and UV/Vis data were recorded with a DAD in the range of 190–600 nm.

5.2.2. Tandem Mass Spectrometry

MS/MS experiments were conducted using two complementary setups: the first employing 3D analysis with a MaXis ESI-TOF-MS system, and the second utilizing 4D analysis with a timsTOF instrument. The key distinction between these setups is the integration of ion mobility spectrometry (IMS) within the timsTOF workflow, which introduces an additional dimension of

separation based on ion shape and size. This enhancement significantly improves the resolution and separation of complex mixtures, enabling more accurate structural characterization and metabolite identification, and ultimately increasing annotation confidence. Both setups were coupled to an UHPLC and DAD systems, ensuring robust separation, detection, and analysis of both crude extracts (0.45 mg/mL) and purified compounds (10-50 µg/mL).

UHPLC-DAD-MS/MS Analysis

HRESI-MS/MS measurements were conducted in positive ion mode using an Agilent 1200 series HPLC-UV system (Agilent Technologies, Böblingen, Germany) coupled to an ESI-TOF-MS (MaXis, Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany). Chromatographic separations were performed under the same conditions as those used for ESI-MS, utilizing a C18 reverse-phase column. The system was calibrated to scan a m/z range of 100–2500. Instrumental settings included a capillary voltage of 4500 V and a dry gas temperature of 200°C to ensure optimal ionization and spectral clarity.

UHPLC-DAD-IM-MS/MS Analysis

Samples were analyzed using an ultrahigh-performance liquid chromatography system (Dionex Ultimate3000RS, Thermo Scientific, Dreieich, Germany) equipped with a C18 column (Kinetex 1.7 µm, 2.1 × 150 mm, 100 Å; Phenomenex). The injection volume of the samples was set to 2 µL. The mobile phase, consisted of A (Milli-Q H₂O + 0.1% formic acid) and B (MeCN + 0.1% formic acid), operated at a constant flow rate of 0.3 mL/min. The gradient started with 1% B for 0.5 min, followed by a linear increase to 5% B in 1 min, then to 100% B over 19 min, and was maintained at this level for 5 min. Throughout the analysis, the column temperature was kept at 40 °C, and UV-Vis data were collected using a DAD within the range of 190–600 nm.

MS spectra in positive ion mode were collected using a timsTOF Pro (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany) with the following parameters: tims ramp time 100 ms, spectra rate 9.52 Hz, PASEF on, cycle time 320 ms, MS/MS scans 2, scan range (m/z , 100–1800 Da; $1/k_0$, 0.55–2.0 V·s/cm²).

5.2.3. Untargeted Metabolomics

For untargeted profiling of the extracts, ESI mass spectra were obtained in positive ion mode. Raw data were pre-processed using MetaboScape® 2022 (Bruker Daltonics) within the retention

time range of 1.0 to 25 min. Features detected in the blank were excluded, while the remaining features were dereplicated against our in-house database comprising MS/MS spectra of standards from characteristic secondary metabolites of Sordariomycetes taxa. In parallel, features were annotated based accurate m/z and MS/MS spectra using the available libraries of metabolites reported in the NP Atlas database. MetaboScape® facilitated automatic *in silico* MS/MS matching using the MetFrag algorithm, relying on the InChI encoded structures, to accomplish this goal in the absence of MS/MS reference data (Ruttkies et al. 2016).

Molecular networks were constructed using the FBMN workflow on the GNPS platform (Wang et al. 2016) with the pre-processed feature table generated in MetaboScape®. The spectra within these networks were matched against GNPS spectral libraries to support metabolite annotation. Visualizations of the resulting networks were created using Cytoscape software (Shannon et al. 2003). Additionally, substructural correlations were explored in depth using the MS2LDA workflow (van der Hooft et al. 2016), and MolNetEnhancer was employed to propagate chemical class annotations across subnetworks (Ernst et al. 2019). To further refine structural annotations, Spec2Vec (Huber et al. 2021) was applied, and the fragmentation patterns of specific compounds were assigned using the CFM-ID 4.0 web server (Wang et al. 2021), SIRIUS (Dührkop et al. 2021) and validated through the SmartFormula 3D tool in MetaboScape®. For additional methodological details, please refer to papers II, IV, VI, IX, XI, XIII, and XIV. Detailed spectral data, links to GNPS results, and relevant annotations are provided in the supplemental material.

5.3. Screening Cultivation and Secondary Metabolite Profiling

To explore secondary metabolite production in selected fungal strains, different liquid and solid media were evaluated. The liquid media included: YM 6.3 (10 g/L malt extract, 4 g/L *D*-glucose, 4 g/L yeast extract, pH 6.3 before autoclaving), Q6 ½ (10 g/L glycerol, 5 g/L cotton seed flour, 2.5 g/L *D*-glucose, pH 7.2 before autoclaving), and ZM ½ (5 g/L molasses, 5 g/L oat flour, 4 g/L mannitol, 4 g/L sucrose, 1.5 g/L CaCO₃, 1.5 g/L *D*-glucose, 0.5 g/L lactalbumin enzymatic hydrolysate, 0.5 g/L (NH₄)₂SO₄, pH 7.2 before autoclaving). For solid media, BRFT and OFT (1 g/L yeast extract, 0.5 g/L K₂HPO₄, 0.5 g/L sodium tartrate; 100 mL solution was added to 28 g brown rice/whole oats before autoclaving) were selected.

In general, each fungal strain was initially cultivated on YM agar (10 g/L malt extract, 4 g/L *D*-glucose, 4 g/L yeast extract, 20 g/L agar, pH 6.3 before autoclaving) at 23 °C. After sufficient mycelial growth, colonies were cut into small pieces (1 cm × 1 cm) using a cork borer, and eight pieces were transferred into 500 mL Erlenmeyer flasks containing 200 mL of the respective screening liquid medium. For solid cultures, an additional 500 mL Erlenmeyer flask containing 200 mL of YM 6.3 was incubated at 23 °C under shaking conditions (140 rpm) in darkness. After 7 days, 6 mL of this seed culture was transferred into a 500 mL Erlenmeyer flask containing BRFT/OFT medium.

Liquid cultures were incubated at 23 °C on a rotary shaker at 140 rpm in the dark, and fermentations were terminated three days after glucose consumption. Glucose levels were monitored daily using Medi-Test Glucose strips (Macherey-Nagel®, Düren, Germany). In contrast, solid cultures were incubated at 23 °C in the dark without shaking and extracted after 15 days of incubation. Further details on the screening cultivation methods can be found in papers IV, VI, and VIII–XIV.

5.4. Secondary Metabolites Extraction

5.4.1. *In vitro* Cultivation

For liquid cultures, the supernatant and mycelia were separated by vacuum filtration using a Büchner funnel lined with a filter disk. The pH of the supernatant was measured with a pH meter, followed by extraction twice with an equal volume of fresh ethyl acetate in a separatory funnel. The combined organic phases were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and evaporated under vacuum using a rotary evaporator at 40 °C. The mycelia were covered with acetone and extracted in an ultrasonic bath at 40 °C for 30 minutes. The acetone solution was filtered through filter paper, and the extraction was repeated once more. The combined acetone solutions were evaporated under vacuum to yield a residual aqueous phase, which was then extracted following the same procedure as described for the supernatant. For solid cultures, the mycelia were first covered with acetone, and the subsequent steps were identical to those used for the mycelia from liquid cultures. To remove the high fatty acid content in the crude extracts from solid cultures, the extracts were dissolved in methanol and extracted twice with heptane. The methanol and

heptane fractions were collected separately and dried under vacuum. All dried crude extracts were dissolved in a 1:1 solution of acetone and methanol, transferred to 4 mL brown glass vials, dried under N₂ flow at 37 °C, and stored at –20 °C until further analysis.

5.4.2. Stromatal Material

To extract secondary metabolites from the fruiting bodies, small stromatal pieces (approx. 1 mm³) were placed in 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes and covered with 1000 µL of methanol. The samples were extracted in an ultrasonic bath at 40 °C for 30 minutes. Afterwards, the tubes were centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 10 minutes. The methanol solution was separated from the stromata, which underwent a second extraction round following the same procedure. The combined organic phases were transferred to 4 mL brown glass vials, dried under N₂ flow at 37 °C, and stored at –20 °C until further analysis.

5.5. Scale-up Cultivation and Extraction

Fungal strains were prioritized for scale-up cultivation based on our metabolomics workflow and their biological activity against bacterial and fungal pathogens during initial screening. To determine the optimal number of shaking flasks required to obtain sufficient material for preparative chromatographic work, variables such as the yield of crude extract per flask, the complexity of the extract, and the presence of targeted metabolites and putative congeners were considered. To ensure reproducibility and standardization, a seed culture was prepared prior to the main cultures. The seed culture followed the protocol for solid culture inoculation outlined in section 2.2. However, in this case, once sufficient mycelial growth was achieved and before glucose was fully consumed, the seed culture was homogenized using an Ultra-Turrax (T25 easy clean digital, IKA) equipped with an S25 N-25F dispersing tool at 10,000 rpm for 10 seconds.

Following inoculation of the main cultures and subsequent glucose depletion, three flasks were selected for small-scale extraction to confirm the production of the targeted metabolites. Under sterile conditions, 2 mL of culture broth were transferred to a 15 mL reaction tubes and extracted with an equal volume of ethyl acetate in an ultrasonic bath at 40 °C for 15 minutes. The organic phases were collected in 4 mL brown glass vials and dried under N₂ flow at 37 °C. The resulting

crude extracts were dissolved in 100 μ L of a 1:1 acetone-methanol solution and analyzed using HPLC-ESI-MS. Once the production of targeted metabolites was confirmed, the main cultures were extracted using the procedure described in section 2.3.1. For the main cultures, the extraction process was repeated at least three times to ensure optimal recovery of secondary metabolites. Further details on the scale-up cultivation methods can be found in papers IV, VI, VIII–X, and XII.

5.6. Purification of Targeted Secondary Metabolites

Initially, crude extracts were pre-fractionated using flash chromatography (Grace Reveleris®, Columbia, MD, USA) with a silica cartridge. The mobile phase generally consisted of solvent A (DCM), solvent B (acetone), and solvent C ([DCM/acetone 8:2]:MeOH). Based on the evaluation of analytical LC-MS data, the resulting fractions were further purified using one of the following systems: reverse-phase HPLC (Büchi Pure C-850, 2020, Switzerland), RP PLC 2250 purification system (Gilson, Middleton, WI, USA), or the Agilent Technologies 1200 Infinity Series semipreparative reverse-phase HPLC. For these separations, various columns were employed as stationary phases, including the Gemini LC column (250 \times 50 mm, 110 Å, 10 μ m; Phenomenex, Aschaffenburg, Germany), Luna C18 (250 \times 21 mm, 7 μ m; Phenomenex, Aschaffenburg, Germany), Synergi™ Polar RP column (250 \times 50 mm, 80 Å, 10 μ m; Phenomenex, Aschaffenburg, Germany), VP Nucleodur 100-5 C18 ec column (150 \times 40 mm, 7 μ m; Macherey-Nagel, Düren, Germany), and XBridge BEH C18 column (250 \times 10 or 19 mm, 5 μ m; Waters, Milford, MA). Flow rates ranged from 5 to 60 mL/min, depending on the column type. Extracts and fractions were divided into multiple aliquots based on the loading capacity of each column. The mobile phase for all separations consisted of solvent A (H₂O + 0.1% formic acid) and solvent B (MeCN + 0.1% formic acid). Additional details regarding UV detection, gradient specifications, and further purification steps for the fractions are provided in papers IV, VI, VIII–X, XII, and XIII.

5.8. Structure Elucidation and Characterization of Pure Metabolites

After assessing the purity and determining the molecular formulae of the isolated metabolites, those of sufficient purity were subjected to NMR spectroscopic analysis. To elucidate their 2D

structural configurations, compounds were dissolved in deuterated solvents depending on their solubility and stability, including acetone-*d*₆, CDCl₃, DMSO-*d*₆, MeOH-*d*₄, or pyridine-*d*₅. For samples exceeding 2 mg, 600 μL of solvent was used in standard 5 mm NMR tubes, while smaller quantities were prepared in 220 μL of the respective solvent and transferred into 3 mm NMR tubes. NMR spectra were acquired using either a Bruker Avance III 700 MHz spectrometer (¹H: 700 MHz, ¹³C: 175 MHz) equipped with a 5 mm TCI cryoprobe or a Bruker Avance III 500 MHz spectrometer (¹H: 500 MHz, ¹³C: 125 MHz) equipped with a BBFO (plus) SmartProbe (Bremen, Germany). One-dimensional ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded in conjunction with two-dimensional ones such as COSY, HSQC, and HMBC for structural elucidation. TOCSY was employed to identify coupled spin systems, facilitating the assignment of overlapping proton signals and improving spectral clarity in complex regions. For the determination of relative stereochemistry, ROESY experiments were performed. Chemical shifts in the NMR spectra were referenced to the signals of the respective deuterated solvents.

Absolute stereochemistry of secondary alcohols was determined by chiral derivatization using Mosher's method (Hoye et al. 2007, Seco et al. 2012). For metabolites containing linear polyene polyketide moieties, chemical degradation via ozonolysis was conducted, and the resulting acids or aldehydes were analyzed using comparative GC-MS. Similarly, fatty acid-substituted metabolites were degraded to their respective fatty acid methyl esters and analyzed via GC-MS. In certain cases, crystal structures were obtained through continuous rotation 3D ED experiments, which provided sufficient resolution to determine the absolute configuration of the respective compounds. Stereochemical assignments were further supported by comparative analysis of spectroscopic data with previously reported reference values. Optical rotation measurements were performed using a MCP 150 polarimeter (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria) or a PerkinElmer 241 polarimeter. UV/Vis spectra were recorded with a Shimadzu UV-2450 spectrophotometer (Kyoto, Japan), while ECD spectra were acquired on a J-815 spectropolarimeter (Jasco, Pfungstadt, Germany).

Further details of the analytical methods, along with structural data, can be found in papers IV, VI, VIII–X, XII, and XIII. Structure elucidation of the compounds reported herein was done by Dr.

Frank Surup and Dr. Sherif S. Ebada, while 3D ED experiments were conducted by Dr. Tatiana E. Gorelik and Dr. Khai-Nghi Truong.

5.9. Biological Activity Assays

To evaluate the potential biological properties of the crude extracts and purified compounds, a series of *in vitro* assays were conducted, including antimicrobial, cytotoxic, and biofilm inhibition assays. These assays provided preliminary therapeutic indications of the tested compounds and guided their prioritization for subsequent testing. Initial screening of the crude extracts was performed to identify candidates with promising antimicrobial activity, integrating the results with the output of our metabolomics analysis. This preliminary evaluation was followed by the targeted purification of bioactive compounds, which were subsequently tested for their specific antimicrobial properties, allowing for a more refined analysis. Cytotoxicity assays were carried out to assess the compounds potential for selective toxicity towards human cells, while biofilm inhibition assays were applied primarily to compounds lacking evident antimicrobial or cytotoxic properties, to assess their ability to inhibit or disrupt bacterial biofilms. Evaluation of pure compounds was carried out by Wera Collisi, biofilm assays were performed by Syeda Javariya Khalid and Dr. Haoxuan Zeng, and anti-CHIKV assays were conducted by Dr. Jackson Muema.

5.9.1. Preliminary Evaluation of Crude Extracts

The antimicrobial activity of the crude extracts was assessed using a serial dilution assay in 96-well microtiter plates. Indicator strains included Gram-positive bacterium *Bacillus subtilis* (DSM 10), Gram-negative bacterium *Escherichia coli* (DSM 1116), the yeast *Candida albicans* (DSM 1665), and the filamentous fungus *Mucor hiemalis* (DSM 2656). To determine the MIC, crude extracts were dissolved in MeOH at a concentration of 4.5 mg/mL. Cell suspensions were prepared and adjusted to the following OD at 600 nm: 0.01 for *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*, and 0.1 for *C. albicans*. For *M. hiemalis*, spores were suspended in MHB and adjusted to 0.01 OD. For the assay, 150 μ L of the microorganism suspensions were dispensed into each well of a 96-well plate. In row A, 130 μ L of the cell suspension was mixed with 20 μ L of the test extract, resulting in a final concentration range of 300–2.35 μ g/mL. Methanol served as the solvent control, while nystatin and ciprofloxacin (starting at 66.6 μ g/mL) were used as positive controls for fungi and

bacteria, respectively. Plates were incubated at 600 rpm on a microplate shaker at 30 °C, except for *E. coli*, which was incubated at 37 °C. MIC values were recorded after 24 hours of incubation, except for *M. hiemalis*, which was evaluated after 48 hours.

5.9.1. Antimicrobial Activity of Pure Compounds

Serial dilution assays were performed in 96 well microtiter plates to determine the MIC against a range of yeasts, filamentous fungi, and bacteria, following the protocol outlined by Harms et al. (2021). The tested microorganisms included *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* (DSM 70572), *C. albicans* (DSM 1665), *Wickerhamomyces anomalus* (DSM 6766), *M. hiemalis* (DSM 2656), *Rhodotorula glutinis* (DSM 10134), *E. coli* (DSM 1116), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (DSM PA14), *Chromobacterium violaceum* (DSM 30191), *B. subtilis* (DSM 10), *Staphylococcus aureus* (DSM 346), and *Mycobacterium smegmatis* (ATCC 700084). Stock solutions of all compounds were prepared in MeOH at a concentration of 1 mg/mL and used in the serial dilution assay. Positive controls for bacteria included the antimicrobials oxytetracycline ([O]), gentamycin ([G]), and kanamycin ([K]), while nystatin ([N]) was used for filamentous fungi and yeast. MeOH (20 µL) was employed as a negative control to demonstrate the absence of inhibitory effects.

5.9.2. Cytotoxic Activity of Pure Compounds

In vitro cytotoxicity assays were performed in 96-well plates according to the procedure outlined by Harms et al. (2021b). Compounds were tested against the mouse fibroblast cell line L929 and cervix carcinoma cell line KB3.1. Active compounds were subsequently evaluated against additional cancer cell lines, including the breast cancer cell line MCF-7, lung cancer cell line A549, ovarian cancer cell line SKOV-3, prostate cancer cell line PC-3, and epidermal cancer cell line A431. Stock solutions of all compounds were prepared in MeOH at a concentration of 1 mg/mL and used for the cytotoxicity assays. Epothilone B served as the positive control, while MeOH (20 µL) was used as the negative control to confirm the absence of inhibitory effects.

5.9.3. Biofilms Assays

Compounds were evaluated for their ability to inhibit biofilm formation by *S. aureus* (DSM 1104) following the established procedure (Soliga et al. 2021). Briefly, serial dilutions of the compounds

(125–7.8 µg/mL) were co-incubated with *S. aureus* in 96-well plates containing CASO medium supplemented with 4% D-glucose. Biofilm inhibition was assessed using Crystal Violet staining after 21 hours of incubation. MAA served as a positive control, and methanol was used as a solvent control. In addition, selected compounds were tested for their ability to disrupt preformed biofilms of *S. aureus* (DSM 1104). Cultures of *S. aureus* (DSM 1104) were prepared by inoculating 1 mL aliquots from a frozen stock (–20 °C) into 25 mL of CASO medium and incubating overnight at 37 °C with shaking at 130 rpm. Biofilm disruption was evaluated using the Crystal Violet assay according to a previously reported procedure (Soliga et al. 2021). Compounds were tested in serial dilutions (250–2 µg/mL), with MeOH and MAA as negative and positive controls, respectively. Statistical differences between samples and controls were determined using a two-tailed Student’s t-test, with statistical significance defined as $p < 0.01$. Statistical analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism 9 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA).

5.9.4. Antiviral Activity

To evaluate the anti-CHIKV effects of selected compounds, Huh 7.5.1 cells (2×10^4 cells/well) were seeded in a 96-well plate and cultured overnight to allow for adherence. The spent culture medium was aspirated, and the cells were incubated for 1 h with 50 µL of compound dilutions at 50 µM in Dulbecco’s modified Eagle medium (DMEM). Subsequently, 50 µL of a wild-type CHIKV suspension at a MOI of 0.1 was added to the respective treatment wells. The cells were then incubated for 72 h under standard culture conditions (37 °C, 5% CO₂). The percentage of cell viability, used as an indirect measure of the antiviral effect (CPE reduction), was determined using a CellTiter-Glo (Promega) assay, following the manufacturer’s instructions. A 0.5% DMSO solution served as the negative control, and ribavirin was used as the positive control.

6. Results

The following section presents the results generated during the course of this thesis, compiled from papers I to XV.

6.1. Establishment of an in-house Fungal Metabolome Library

A primary objective of this thesis was to establish a solid framework for the development of an in-house database of fungal metabolites, specifically derived from taxonomically pre-selected species within the class Sordariomycetes. Particularly, purified compounds and crude extracts derived from cultures and stromata of taxa within the family Hypoxylaceae were employed as a starting point, since this group has been extensively studied during previous screening campaigns. This database served as a valuable resource for this pilot study. Accordingly, the first chapter of this section provides a general overview of this fungal metabolite repository. However, an in-depth analysis of the database is not included, as the data remain unpublished and cannot yet be fully disclosed. The construction and integration of this database at an early stage of our screening workflow were fundamental to the success of this thesis.

Ever since the field of metabolomics started to expand and became integrated into diverse natural product discovery programs, a substantial gap has persisted in the representation of fungal metabolites within public repositories (Zuffa et al. 2024). In contrast to bacterial metabolites, which have been extensively studied and characterized over the past decades, fungal secondary metabolites remain significantly underrepresented in spectral databases such as MassBank or GNPS. This challenge is partly due to the historical focus on bacterial natural products for drug discovery, driven by their faster and more straightforward cultivation, a more advanced understanding of their biology, and the availability of well-established high-throughput methodologies (Cánovas et al. 2017). Fungi, on the other hand, have long been overlooked, and only recently have efforts begun to unravel the complexity of their biosynthetic potential and the underlying principles governing it (Bills and Gloer 2016, Cox 2024).

Despite the focus of the following chapters on relatively unexplored or novel taxa, prior knowledge from other taxonomic groups suggests that redundancies can be expected when

studying closely related species, as observed in *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, or even Myxobacteria (Frisvad 2015, Hoffmann et al. 2018). Similarly, within certain lineages of the Xylariales, such as the Hypoxylaceae, the pigments found in their stromata often share similar chemical profiles, as previously discussed (Section 3.2). Therefore, the implementation of dereplication strategies proves invaluable for the rapid detection of known chemical scaffolds and their putative analogs, enabling the efficient prioritization of strains with novel chemistry (Figure 6). This approach not only minimizes redundancies but also streamlines the identification and selection of novel compounds with promising biological properties.

To provide a brief overview of the established library, the advantages of the employed methodology are discussed, while further details can be found in the materials and methods section. UHPLC-DAD-MS/MS has long been the gold standard for characterizing small molecules in both targeted and untargeted metabolomics workflows. However, this technology does not fully capture the complexity of natural products, particularly when spatial characteristics such as stereoisomeric configuration, which significantly influence biological properties, are taken into account. To address this limitation, novel technologies, including IMS, have been integrated into mass spectrometry workflows over the past decades (Heuckeroth et al. 2024). IMS introduces an additional dimension to metabolomics by rapidly separating ions based on their collision cross-sections (CCS) in a carrier gas, enabling isomer separation, signal filtering, and more confident metabolite annotation through CCS matching and prediction. The analysis of small molecules by UHPLC-DAD-IMS-MS/MS enables comprehensive feature annotation based on high-resolution m/z , MS/MS spectra, retention time, CCS values, and UV/Vis spectra (Figure 6). This multidimensional approach, commonly referred to as 4D-metabolomics, is still an emerging field, but its efficient integration into discovery pipelines is expected to enhance our understanding of fungal chemical diversity, the central focus of this thesis. By establishing a curated fungal metabolome library using 4D-metabolomics, this study contributes to close this gap in fungal metabolite annotation and provides a valuable resource to facilitate future discovery efforts. The integration of IMS in this workflow represents a key advancement, improving the accuracy of metabolite characterization, particularly for structurally complex compounds. These efforts will

contribute to a more comprehensive and accessible representation of fungal secondary metabolites, ultimately improving their incorporation into natural product discovery pipelines.

Figure 6. Overview of the metabolomics workflow for establishing our in-house fungal metabolome library. (A) The library includes isolated metabolites with full structural elucidation, stromatal extracts from herbarium specimens, and culture extracts from taxonomically well-identified species. (B) The data structure within the metabolome library, obtained after processing with MetaboScope, enables confident metabolite annotation based on retention time, accurate mass, cross-collisional cross-sectional values, and MS/MS spectra comparison.

By using 4D-metabolomics, we established a comprehensive library of secondary metabolites derived from taxa within the Sordariomycetes, with particular focus on the Hypoxylaceae family. This repository currently comprises ~180 authenticated standards of secondary metabolites, previously characterized through comprehensive structural elucidation techniques, including HR-

MS, NMR, and, in some cases, X-ray crystallography or 3D electron diffraction (3D-ED). Figure 7 provides an overview of the chemical properties of the metabolites included in this repository. The molecular weights span ~150 to ~1300 Da, with the majority between 350 and 600 Da (Figure 7A). The metabolites were classified based on their biosynthetic origins, covering polyketide, NRPS-like, NRPS, PKS-NRPS, terpene, and meroterpenoid pathways. Notably, polyketides and PKS-NRPS hybrids represented the most abundant classes (Figure 7B), consistent with the biosynthetic potential reported for members of the Hypoxylaceae. Furthermore, the elemental compositions of these metabolites were relatively conserved across the dataset, except for specific classes such as large cyclodepsipeptides and certain meroterpenoids featuring unique structural moieties (Figure 7C).

Moving forward, the fungal metabolome library will continue to expand in taxonomic coverage while benefiting from advances in machine learning-assisted spectral interpretation and enhanced genome-metabolome linkages. These efforts provide a foundation for integrating multi-omics approaches to explore fungal biosynthetic diversity, evolution, and ecological roles. The recent availability of high-quality genomes from Hypoxylaceae members will facilitate large-scale genomic and metabolomics analyses, enabling the systematic pairing of GCFs with molecular families (MFs). In parallel, incorporating bioactivity data will allow for the targeted prioritization of GCF-MF links with desirable biological effects. Beyond establishing gene-metabolite correlations, this approach represents a conceptual shift toward understanding how biosynthetic pathways shape the biological functions of their products, ultimately advancing fungal natural product discovery.

Figure 7. Overview of the fungal metabolome library. (A) Molecular weight distribution of compounds within the library. (B) Distribution of biosynthetic classes among the identified compounds. (C) Elemental composition of compounds, showing the relative abundance of key elements.

6.2. Diversity of Biologically Active Secondary Metabolites in the Ascomycete Order Sordariales

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6.3. Segregation of the Genus *Parahypoxylon* (Hypoxylaceae, Xylariales) from *Hypoxylon* a Polyphasic Taxonomic Approach

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6.4. Studies on the Genus *Pyrenopolyporus* (Hypoxylaceae) in Thailand Using a Polyphasic Taxonomic Approach

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6.5. *Amesia hispanica* sp. nov., Producer of the Antifungal Class of Antibiotics Dactylfungins

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6.6. Metabolomics Insights into the Polyketide-Lactones Produced by *Diaporthe caliensis* sp. nov., an Endophyte of the Medicinal Plant *Otoba gracilipes*

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6.7. Bioprospection of Tenellins Produced by the Entomopathogenic Fungus *Beauveria neobassiana*

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6.8. Depicting the Chemical Diversity of Bioactive Meroterpenoids Produced by the Largest Organism on Earth

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6.9. Neochetracin: An Unusual Chetracin-Type Epithiodiketopiperazine Derivative Produced by the Fungus *Amesia atrobrunnea*

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6.10. Integrative Taxonomy of *Metarhizium anisopliae* Species Complex, Based on Phylogenomics Combined with Morphometrics, Metabolomics, and Virulence Data

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6.11. Arcopilins: A New Family of *Staphylococcus aureus* Biofilm Disruptors from the Soil Fungus *Arcopilus navicularis*

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6.12. Reaping the Chemical Diversity of *Morinagamyces vermicularis* Using Feature-Based Molecular Networking

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6.13. Tailored culture strategies to promote antimicrobial secondary metabolite production in *Diaporthe caliensis*: a metabolomic approach

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7. Conclusion and Outlook

The remarkable ability of fungi to produce biologically active secondary metabolites is unquestionable, as thoroughly discussed in the previous sections. Yet as our understanding of their secondary metabolite diversity grows, new questions and challenges emerge, many of which became evident as part of this thesis. While untapped taxa from the orders Xylariales and Sordariales represent promising targets for further discovery campaigns, recent taxonomic revisions within these groups highlight the importance of integrative approaches that consider their evolutionary relationships, which is in fact deeply linked to their chemistry.

These approaches can provide deeper insights into the mechanisms driving secondary metabolite diversification and their ecological adaptations. This might prove useful for the search of novel natural products by exploiting our understanding on the parallel evolution of these lineages and their biosynthetic arsenal. With recent advancements in genomics, obtaining full genome sequences from these novel producers is feasible within a reasonable timeframe, enabling targeted studies that link our expertise on natural product chemistry with genome mining studies in an integrated fashion. For example, the recent availability of 60 genomes from representatives of the Hypoxylaceae family paves the way for large-scale analyses of the evolutionary dynamics, ecological roles, and diversification of biosynthetic gene clusters within this group.

However, to enable the targeted prioritization of molecules with desirable biological effects or ecological relevance, it is necessary to integrate phenotypic and metabolomic datasets into our analysis pipeline. The proposed workflows and derived findings presented in this thesis lay the foundation for combining metabolomics, genome mining, and phenotypic profiling within ongoing large-scale metabologenomic efforts aimed at systematically linking biosynthetic pathways to their corresponding natural products and biological functions. This integrative framework offers a roadmap for exploring the vast and uncharted fungal chemical space. Importantly, future work building on the results of this thesis will embark on constructing a conceptual shift, from simple gene-metabolite correlations to a deeper understanding of the functional relationships between biosynthetic genes and their products.

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